

THE IMPORTANCE OF CONTENT AND LANGUAGE INTEGRATED LEARNING IN TEACHING

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ABSTRACT: CLIL- Content and Language Integrated Learning. 'CLIL is an approach in which a foreign language is used as a tool in the learning of a non-language subject in which both. language and the subject have a joint role.' (Marsh in Coyle: 2006)

Keywords: Content, Language, English, cognition, improving language, improving cognitive skills

What is CLIL?

Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) is a dual -focused instructional method wherein an extra language is used for the mastering and coaching of each content material and language. That is, withinside the coaching and gaining knowledge of process, there's a focal point now no longer simplest on content material, and now no longer most effective on language. Each is interwoven, despite the fact that the emphasis is more on one or the alternative at a given time.

CLIL isn't always a brand new shape of language training. It isn't a brand new shape of subject schooling. It is an revolutionary fusion of each. CLIL is intently associated with and stocks a few factors of a variety of academic practices. Some of these practices - including bilingual schooling and immersion - were in operation for many years in precise international locations and contexts; others, which includes content material-based language coaching or English as an Additional Language (EAL), may also proportion a few fundamental theories and exercise however aren't synonymous with CLIL because there are a few essential differences. CLIL is content material-driven, and that is wherein it each extends the enjoy of getting to know a language, and wherein it will become extraordinary to present language coaching approaches. Throughout this book, we can make clear the evolving CLIL phenomenon through exploring middle concepts which permeate special applications. Whilst CLIL is bendy and may be tailored to unique contexts, nonetheless, for the technique to be justifiable and sustainable, its theoretical foundation need to be rigorous and obvious in exercise. The time period CLIL is inclusive in that it binds collectively the essence of right exercise observed withinside the one of a kind environments wherein its concepts were adopted. It includes a variety of fashions which may be carried out in a number of methods with various kinds of learner. Good CLIL

exercise is found out thru techniques which give a more holistic instructional revel in for the learner than can also additionally in any other case be commonly achievable.

CLIL involves learning to use language appropriately whilst using language to learn effectively. It is built on the following principles:

1 Content matter is not only about acquiring knowledge and skills, it is about the learner creating their own knowledge and understanding and developing skills (personalized learning).

2 Content is related to learning and thinking (cognition). To enable the learner to create their own interpretation of content, it must be analysed for its linguistic demands.

3 Thinking processes (cognition) need to be analysed for their linguistic demands. 4 Language needs to be learned which is related to the learning context, to learning through that language, to reconstructing the content, and to related cognitive processes. This language needs to be transparent and accessible. 5 Interaction in the learning context is fundamental to learning. This has implications when the learning context operates through the medium of a foreign language. 6 The relationship between cultures and languages is complex. Intercultural awareness is fundamental to CLIL.

7 CLIL is embedded in the wider educational context in which it is developed and therefore must take account of contextual variables in order to be effectively realized. In the 4Cs Framework, the terms 'language' and 'communication' are used interchangeably. This is not only a syntactical device for promoting the C concepts, but also a strategy for promoting genuine communication in the vehicular language if learning is to take place. It is an attempt to redress the criticism made by Donato that poorly conceived language experiences 'educate learners towards communicative incompetence rather than competence' (1996). We considered it necessary to divide advantages of using CLIL according to the different beneficiaries of this approach in order to highlight that using CLIL can give many opportunities to children, teachers and the community at large. There are a number of benefits of CLIL we would like to indicate: students' motivation for learning, development of their autonomous learning, educational and methodological innovation for the community, as well as teachers' motivation arising from team work and from the collaboration with other teachers.

Improving language and subject knowledge

Using CLIL in primary school will allow students to use language purposefully, to effectively process information, negotiate understanding and assemble

knowledge. This approach of learning is rooted within the socio-constructivist and co-operative teaching and studying methods and activities.

A useful tool in this respect is to create a bilingual school room with interactive posters containing: all time expressions (calendar: date, day of the week, months, seasons, time of day, year);

cardinal and ordinal numbers; the maximum common adjectives (e.g. emoticons); names of school subjects; a set of school room rules; vocabulary linked to meals and drink, common animals, the weather, etc.

Improving cognitive skills

For people learning an extra language in a CLIL context supports the improvement of first language communication skills and literacy, as well as progressed cognitive skills in the areas of higher-order and critical thinking. It additionally contributes to strengthening cognitive and general learning abilities such as creative and critical thinking. Language learning uses and develops specific and specific conceptualisation skills and meta-cognition. The inexperienced persons in primary school think and make sense of knowledge, experience by remembering, understanding, evaluating, critiquing, reflecting and creating.

Developing intercultural communication and knowledge

Because CLIL is strongly associated with both content place and overseas language, it is naturally imbedded with intercultural communication and knowledge which have social significance. The learners will broaden a stronger understanding of an intercultural dimension as a result of CLIL methodology and will be more likely to see the big picture in terms of the relationship between language and society. The exposure to alternative perspectives and views helps build intercultural knowledge, awareness and understanding. CLIL can help develop intercultural communication skills as well as learning about other European countries, regions or minority groups. This helps introduce children to a wider cultural context thus enhancing their participation in a European society.

Promoting active learning

CLIL involves a change of focus in the classroom. When teachers use the school lingua franca for teaching, they can tell the students everything they want them to know, and the students can understand them. However, when they teach their subject using a new language, this isn't possible. Because of this, they have to show students how to find out information for themselves, and how to work and

talk together to discover new ideas, so that using the language becomes part of the process of learning. In other words, the teachers have to change their methodology, and find different ways to help students learn.

By doing this, the trainer prepares younger college students for the current world, wherein human beings paintings in venture teams; use different languages to speak to numerous colleagues and to speak with humans in special countries. They are anticipated to resolve problems, plan their personal paintings and find out matters for themselves the usage of a variety of sources, mainly the Internet.

Developing getting to know, verbal exchange and social techniques CLIL implementation can provide software and shipping of numerous getting to know techniques that may lead to new possibilities for enforcing man or woman coaching and mastering patterns and techniques. In fact, CLIL gives opportunity approaches of drawing close language mastering, which can lessen student exclusion and can serve mainstream inexperienced persons well. Even alevn though CLIL favours variety of techniques and sorts of study room practice, a not unusualplace function of many CLIL methodologies is the synergy which ends from the juxtaposition of the verbal exchange orientation of language studying, the hobby in content material, and the interplay which takes location in the lecture room. The end result promotes person getting to know techniques and interactive methodologies and leads to multiplied learner motivation, bringing extra blessings for studying.

The CLIL method recognises that mastering isn't a in basic terms inner and cognitive process, but rather outcomes from interplay wherein know-how and information are shared. Through interplay, newcomers construct on their present know-how as they speak it and examine with new content material and new language. At the identical time, they end up aware about what they nevertheless want to do. For language gaining knowledge of particularly, interplay gives an possibility to each examine and improve.

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